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INFLUENCE OF BUILDING SPATIAL LAYOUT ON PASSIVE INDOOR THERMAL AND VISUAL COMFORT IN MIDRISE-OFFICE BUILDING IN TEMPERATE DRY CLIMATE OF NIGERIA

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Abstract

Studies have shown that, people prefer to live in a passive indoor environment than the contrary, and one of the factors affecting that is the spatial building layout. Researchers have different views on the best building spatial layout for thermal and visual comfort in the tropics. This research is aimed at exploring the influence of the spatial building layout on passive indoor thermal and visual comfort (PITVC) in mid-rise office buildings in temperate dry climate of Nigeria. It was done by using three (3) different building spatial layout (single-banked, double-banked, and open planned) of midrise office building to determine the differences in daylight autonomy (DA), useful daylight illuminance ($UDI_{100-3000}$), spatial daylight autonomy (sDA), operative temperature (OT) and relative humidity (RH). Data was collected from simulation of the prototype single-banked, double-banked, and open planned office buildings, using google Sketch-Up 2017 and open-studio simulation tool which was done on the hypothetical sites devoid of surrounding buildings and trees, in Jalingo, Minna, Zaria, and Abuja. Data generated were then analysed using ANOVA, bar charts, column charts, graphs, and Tables with significance threshold of 0.05. The study shows that, DA, sDA, and $UDI_{100-3000}$ values of single-banked office building were 315%, 116.4%, and 224% relative to that of double-bank office buildings respectively, and 200%, 100%, 128.7% relative to that of open planned office buildings respectively. It was also noted that single banked has the lowest mean value of operative temperature and highest mean value of relative humidity, followed by open-planned-office building and then double-banked. The one way ANOVA shows the difference between the single-banked, double-banked and open-plan offices in their DA, UDI, sDA and relative humidity are statistically significant, $df(2, 21) = 834.9, p = .0000$; $df(2, 21) = 28.9.9, p = .0000$; and $df(2, 21) = 234.2, p = .0000$, and $df(2, 21) = 50.1, p = .0000$ respectively. The study recommends that the three (3) building spatial layout must have different orientations, window to wall ration, R-values, building materials and other architectural variables to achieve PIETV in temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

Keywords: Daylight autonomy, Operative temperature, Spatial Building layout, Thermal comfort, Visual comfort.

1.0 Introduction

An office building is a type of commercial building which encloses architectural spaces, planned to be used for office work. Workers spend an average of 8 hours indoor in their offices daily especially those working in multi storey office buildings. Passive Indoor Thermal and Visual Comfort (PITVC) is simply a condition of architectural space where thermal and daylight quantity and quality are optimum and maintained for a period of time. One of the main issue affecting the quest for PITVC is the building spatial layout as observed by Kennedy and Thompson (2011). St Clair (2009) concluded that, single-banked buildings are more suitable for the climate than the double-banked buildings, while Crosby (2009) believes in the contrary. A number of researchers such as Astrich, Morris, and Walters (2010); Samir, Nouredine and Abdelhalim (2017); Givoni (1994); and Reynolds (2002) have noted that,

building spatial layout have impact on the indoor environmental comfort requirements of the buildings.

The aim of this study is to explore the impacts of spatial layout on passive indoor thermal and visual comfort (PITVC) in mid-rise office buildings in temperate dry climate of Nigeria. It was done by using single-banked, double-banked, and open planned midrise office building prototypes to determine the differences in the daylight autonomy (DA), useful daylight illuminance (UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀), spatial daylight autonomy (sDA), operative temperature (OT) and relative humidity (RH). These brought about the following hypothesis: The null hypothesis (H₀) states that, the mean effects of PITVC is significantly the same for all the three different types of building spatial layout, while the alternative hypothesis (H₁) states that, the mean effects of PITVC is significantly different for at least of the building spatial layout.

The classifications of office buildings vary from Engineering, Estate managers to Architecture points of view. For example, Building Owners and Managers Association BOMA (2012) identified office buildings as *A*, *B*, and *C* types depending on the location and level of luxury, while Erkini (2016) categorised office buildings based on building heights, as normal (for those with 3-36m height or 1-12 floors), high-rise structures (with 37-75m height or 12-25 floors) and skyscrapers (those with more than 75m height or more than 25 floors). Alcox, (2017) classified multi-story buildings as a low-rise office building with less than 4 floors; mid-rise building, which has a range of 4-12 floors; high-rise building, with 12 to 40 floors; skyscraper, which has more than 40 floors but less than 300m high; super tall buildings, which has a height of 300m to 600m; and mega tall building, with a height greater than 600m. A mid-rise office building in this study is any office with 4 to 12 floors, as classified by Alcox (2017) and Freedman (2009).

There are various ways to classify office buildings in architecture as noted by Musa (2022) which include: classification based on form; circulation pattern; accessibility; building layout; and so on, as shown in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1. 1. Classification of office buildings
Source: Musa, (2022)

This study is using classification based on accessibility of passive indoor environmental comfort as contained in figure 1.1.

There are many climate classifications in relation to Nigeria such as Köppen, Thornthwaite, Atkinson, and many others, however, the study has adopted Mobolade and Pourvahidi's (2020) climate classification based on the fact that it factored temperature, relative humidity, mean radiant temperature and wind velocity in its method of classification. It also considers the gradual transition from one climatic zone to another.

2.0 Materials and Methods

A quantitative research design using an explorative design approach was employed in the study as well as an experimental research strategy through simulation method to assess the PITVC. A convenience non-probability sampling technique was used in selecting the iterative prototypes of single-banked, double-banked and open-planned office building, which are Bank of Industry, Federal Secretariat, and Bayero University Senate Buildings respectively all in Nigeria as indicated in plate 1 and 2.

Plate 1. The corridor of Bank of Industry

Plate 2. Office in Bayero University Senate Building.

This is due to the fact that the Federal Secretariat and Bank of Industry buildings are replicated all over the temperate dry climate of Nigeria. Other criteria used in the selection was the difference in their orientations, building spatial layout, relative positions in the climate, number of storeys (mid-rise buildings), access to buildings, and Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning systems. The Prototypes were modelled using google Sketch-Up 2017 and OpenStudio simulation tool from January to December 2023 on the hypothetical sites devoid of surrounding buildings and trees, in Jalingo, Minna, Zaria, and Abuja, and their mean values were used as indicated in Plate 3.

Plate 3. Floor plan of the prototypes of double-banked, single-banked and Open-plan midrise office buildings in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria respectively (from left to right).

The procedure used in conducting the research is based on the following documents: Daylighting Monitoring Protocols and Procedures for Buildings, 1997; Monitoring Procedures for Assessment of Daylighting Performance of Buildings, 2001 (both published by the International Energy Agency IEA); Lighting handbook, reference and application (2000); Illuminating Engineering Society (2012); 2015 International Energy Conservation Code, USA; and ASHRAE standards 55 (2020).

Thirty (30) offices from each of the single-banked, double-banked and open-plan office buildings were used and of the same dimensions, orientation, window to wall ratio, openable window to floor area ratio, and height. Data generated were then analysed using ANOVA, bar charts, column charts, graphs, and tables.

3.0 Findings and Discussion

The simulation results for the effects of spatial layout on PITVC concerning DA, UDI, sDA, operative temperature, and relative humidity for single-banked, double-banked and open-planed midrise office buildings are presented in Tables 3.1, 3.12, and 3.3 respectively.

Table 3.1. Simulation results of a single-banked prototype midrise office building

DA(%)	UDI(%)	sDA(%)	OT(OC)	RH(%)
83.25	78.75	99	27	65.3
84.5	80.25	99.25	31.4	61.5
84.5	79	99	31.8	62
84.5	79.75	99	32	56.5
84	79.75	99.25	32	60
83.75	80.25	99	31.7	56.5
84.5	79.25	99	32	59.5
84.5	79.25	99	29	65.2
Mean value=				
84.1875	79.53125	99.0625	30.8625	60.8125

Table 3.2. Simulation results of a double-banked prototype office building

DA(%)	UDI(%)	SDA(%)	OT(°C)	RH(%)
28	75.75	45.25	32.5	49
29	80.5	50.25	31.5	48
28.5	81.25	50.75	32.1	50
28.75	81.75	51.25	30	48
27.5	80	49.5	32	50
28.5	80.5	50.75	32	50
29	80.75	50.75	32.2	47
28	82	49.75	30.5	50
Mean value =				
28.40625	80.3125	49.78125	31.6	49

Table 3.3 Simulation results of an open-plan prototype office building

DA(%)	UDI(%)	SDA(%)	OT(⁰ C)	RH(%)
32	84	59	28.7	57.3
39	85	79	30.7	55.8
44	84	80	30.3	54.8
41	84	79	31.7	53.8
38	85	76	32.2	54.8
45	84	83	31.2	51.4
46	83	82	31.9	53.8
46	83	80	29.7	51.8
Mean value				
41.375	84	77.25	30.8	54.1875

The descriptive statistics showed the glaring differences among single-banked, double-banked, and open-plan office building in the annual mean of UDI, DA, sDA, OT, and RH. The DA, sDA, and UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀ values of single-banked office buildings are 315%, 116.4%, and 224% of that of the double-banked office buildings respectively, and 200%, 100%, 128.7% of that of the open-planned office buildings in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria as indicated in Figure 3.1 to 3.5.

Figure 3.1. Comparison of spatial layout on DA

Figure 3.2. Comparison of spatial layout on UDI

Figure 3.3. Comparison of spatial layout on sDA.

Figure 3.4. Comparison of spatial layout on operative temperature.

Figure 3.5. Comparison of spatial layout on relative humidity.

It would also be noted that, single banked office building has the lowest mean value of operative temperature and highest value of mean relative humidity, followed by open-planned-office building and then double-banked, as indicated in Figure 3.1 to 3.5.

3.1 Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: The null hypothesis states that, the mean effects of PITVC is significantly the same for all the three different types of building spatial layout.

The data were tested for skewness and kurtosis and found to be within the acceptable range of values as specified by George and Mallery, (2010). The one way ANOVA showed the difference between the single-banked, double-banked and open-planned offices in their DA, UDI, sDA and RH are statistically significant, $df(2, 21) = 834.9, p = .0000$; $df(2, 21) = 28.9.9, p = .0000$; and $df(2, 21) = 234.2, p = .0000$, and $df(2, 21) = 50.1, p = .0000$ respectively.

4.0 Conclusion

The null hypothesis is therefore rejected and the study concludes that building spatial layout has significant influence on the passive indoor thermal and visual comfort (PITVC) in mid-rise office buildings in temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

5.0 Implication of the study

The study recommends that the three (3) building spatial layout (single-banked, double-banked, and open-plan) must have different orientations, window to wall ration, R-values, building materials and other architectural variables to achieve passive thermal and visual comfort in temperate dry climate of Nigeria. Which means that, each should have a different framework for PITVC in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

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